

Agricultural Land Ownership in the United States: Recent Issues

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Abstract

La production agricole dans les fermes et les ranchs contribue de manière significative au produit intérieur brut et à l'emploi total des États-Unis. Cet article se concentre brièvement sur les exploitations et les terres agricoles aux États-Unis. Il aborde l'importance des femmes dans l'agriculture américaine et met ensuite en évidence les programmes visant à faciliter l'accès aux terres agricoles pour des groupes particuliers d'agriculteurs. Bien que le transfert de terres agricoles ne soit soumis qu'à peu de restrictions, la propriété étrangère des terres agricoles est un sujet de préoccupation croissant. L'article examine donc les exigences fédérales en matière de divulgation pour les propriétaires étrangers, ainsi que les restrictions imposées par les États sur la propriété des étrangers et des sociétés.

Die landwirtschaftliche Produktion auf Farmen und Ranches trägt erheblich zum Bruttoinlandsprodukt der USA und zur Gesamtbeschäftigung bei. Dieser Artikel befasst sich kurz mit Farmen und landwirtschaftlichen Flächen in den Vereinigten Staaten. Er geht auf die Bedeutung von Frauen in der US-Landwirtschaft ein und beleuchtet dann Programme, die speziellen Gruppen von Landwirten den Zugang zu landwirtschaftlichen Flächen erleichtern. Obwohl die Übertragung von landwirtschaftlichen Flächen nur wenigen Beschränkungen unterliegt, gibt das ausländische Eigentum an landwirtschaftlichen Flächen zunehmend Anlass zur Sorge. In dem Artikel werden daher die bundesstaatlichen Offenlegungspflichten für ausländische Eigentümer sowie die bundesstaatlichen Beschränkungen für ausländisches und unternehmerisches Eigentum erörtert.

Introduction

Agricultural production on farms and ranches contributes significantly to the US gross domestic product and total employment.¹ This Article focuses briefly on farms and farmland in the United States. It addresses the importance of women in US agriculture and then highlights programs to facilitate access

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¹ Agriculture, food, and related industries contributed 5.4% to the 2021 US gross domestic product and represented 10.4% of 2022 total employment. Farm cash receipts in 2022 totaled \$555 billion from crops, animals, and animal products, with 52% from crops and 48% from animals and their products. See USDA, ERS, *Ag and Food Sectors and the Economy* (last updated 3 Nov. 2023), <https://www.ers.usda.gov/data-products/ag-and-food-statistics-charting-the-essentials/ag-and-food-sectors-and-the-economy/>; USDA, ERS, *Farm Income and Wealth Data Product* (31 Aug. 2023).

to agricultural land for special groups of farmers. Although the transfer of agricultural land is subject to few restrictions, foreign ownership of farmland is an increasing matter of concern. The Article therefore discusses federal disclosure requirements for foreign owners, as well as state restrictions on foreign and corporate ownership.

1. US Agricultural Land

A. Land Area

The United States has a total land area of about 2.3 billion acres (1 hectare is 2.469 acres), with land and water areas of about 1.94 billion acres. Almost 1.4 billion acres (71%) are nonfederal rural land: cropland (368 million acres, with 52 million uncultivated), rangeland (404 million), pasture (122 million), and forest (418 million).² Prime farmland totals 314 million acres.³ Urban uses are only a small percentage of US land.⁴

More than 60% of US land is privately owned, including 98% of cropland, 63% of pasture and range, and 57% of forest.⁵ State law governs most aspects of ownership and use of privately-owned land.

The federal government owns about 28% of US land (about 640 million acres), with federal lands located in every state, but primarily in Alaska and the mountainous West. Four federal agencies -- Bureau of Land Management, Forest Service, Fish and Wildlife Service, National Park Service -- administer 95% of this land under management priorities prescribed by federal law.⁶

B. Farms and Farmland: Census of Agriculture Data

The 2022 Census of Agriculture, published in 2024,⁷ provides details about US farms and farmland. The United States had 1.9 million farms,⁸ which occupied about 880 million acres of land (including 382 million acres of cropland).⁹ The average farm size was 463 acres, and the majority of farms were small, both in size and in value of sales. Almost 1.4 million farms had annual sales of less than \$50,000, and 1.33 million were smaller than 180 acres. About 178,000 farms had sales over \$500,000, and nearly

² USDA, 2017 National Resources Inventory, Summary Report, at 2-1 to 2-3 (2020). Total land and water area includes the 48 contiguous states, plus Hawaii, Puerto Rico, and the US Virgin Islands.

³ Prime farmland "has the best combination of physical and chemical characteristics for producing food, feed, forage, fiber, and oilseed crops and is also available for these uses." Since 1982, prime farmland has decreased from 328.9 to 313.7 million acres; 65% of prime farmland is cropland. *Id.* at 5-2 to 5-3.

⁴ Developed land in 2017 was about 116 million acres (an increase of 61% since 1982), including large and small urban and built-up areas and rural transportation. *Id.* at 2-6.

⁵ Daniel P. Bigelow & Allison Borchers, Major Uses of Land in the United States, 2012, at 42-45 (ERS, USDA, EIB 178, 2017) (latest edition). Private land includes land in foreign ownership. See 4.A in this Article. State and local governments own about 8% of US land.

⁶ Carol Hardy Vincent et al., Federal Land Ownership: Overview and Data, at 1 (CRS R42346, 2020); Katie Hoover, Federal Lands and Related Resources: Overview and Selected Issues for the 118th Congress, at 1 (CRS R43429, Feb. 2023).

⁷ National Agricultural Statistics Service (NASS), USDA, 2022 Census of Agriculture, United States Summary and State Data, vol. 1 (AC-22-A-51, 2024). USDA will release data from the 2022 Census in 2024.

⁸ *Id.* At 3, Table 1. A farm is "any place from which \$1,000 or more of agricultural products were produced and sold, or normally would have been sold, during the census year." *Id.* at viii.

⁹ In 2022, the number of farms was estimated at 2.003 million, with total land in farms at 893.4 million acres and an average farm size of 446 acres. NASS, Farms and Land in Farms: 2022 Summary, at 4 (Feb. 2023).

160,000 were larger than 1,000 acres. Large farms occupied the majority of US farmland; more than 83,000 farms had 2,000 or more acres (average size 6,444 acres). Over the past decades, crop production has consolidated on increasingly larger farms, including family farms. Most farms are operated by individuals or families, with only about 15% operated by partnerships, corporations, or other entities.¹⁰ Most farm partnerships and corporations, however, are family enterprises.

Although about 60% of US farmland is operated by owners, tenancy is significant in US agriculture, especially for grain production. Almost 40% of US farmland is rented, with a higher percentage in some states.¹¹ In 2022, full owners operated 71.4% of farms (average size, 230 acres), but farm tenants operated larger farms. Part owners occupied 22.3% of farms (average size, 1,155 acres) and full tenants, 6.3% (average size, 655 acres).¹² Owners of rented land are individuals (e.g., retired farmers or heirs of farmland); legal entities such as partnerships, corporations, trusts; and other owners. Few farm operators rent out land, and as farmers age, they tend to own more farmland.¹³ Tenancy gives younger operators access to farmland,

2. Women in US Agriculture

About 2.6 million people work on US farms.¹⁴ Women participate actively in US agriculture. In 2022, 36% (1.2 million) of the 3.4 million producers were female.¹⁵ The Census of Agriculture defines a producer as a person “involved in making decisions for the farm operation,” and farms often have more than one producer. In 2017, about 56% of farms had one or more female producers; 91% of farms had one or more male producers. Fewer women (798,500) were principal producers -- persons who identified as principal operators. Fewer still (489,000) identified as primary producers -- persons who made the most decisions for the farm.¹⁶ In 2022, most female producers resided on the farm they operated, and they were involved in day-to-day operations, as well as decisions about land use and crops, livestock, marketing, financial management, and succession planning. But farming was not the primary occupation of 66% of female producers.¹⁷

In several characteristics, female and male producers differed. The average age of female producers was slightly younger than males, and female producers were more likely to be beginning farmers (with

¹⁰ NASS, *supra* note 7, at 3, 13, 88-89, 171-172, Tables 1, 7, 71, 74. Data from a smaller survey is reported in Christine Whitt et al., *America’s Farms and Ranches at a Glance: 2022 Edition* (ERS, USDA, EIB 247, 2022). Data from 2021 indicated that 98% of farms, with 83% of production, were family farms.

¹¹ Daniel Bigelow et al., *U.S. Farmland Ownership, Tenure, and Transfer*, at 15-17 (ERS, USDA, EIB 161, 2016) (based on a 2014 survey). Figures for 48 contiguous states totaled “354 million acres of rented agricultural land owned by 2.13 million landlord entities.” *Id.* at 17.

¹² NASS, *supra* note 7, at 228, Table 76.

¹³ Bigelow et al., *supra* note 11, at 10-11, 15.

¹⁴ USDA, *Ag and Food Sectors*, *supra* note 1 (2022 data).

¹⁵ The questionnaire for CEDR 2023 Commission III asked for information about the status of women in agriculture. For a recent analysis, see Caitlin Joseph et al., *The State of Gender Equity in U.S. Agriculture* (American Farmland Trust, 2024).

¹⁶ National Agricultural Statistics Service (NASS), USDA, 2017 Census of Agriculture, United States Summary and State Data, vol. 1 (AC-17-A-51, 2019), at 62, Table 52; Appendix B, at 19-20 (Census definitions). Analogous data does not appear in the 2022 Census.

¹⁷ NASS, *supra* note 7, at 62-63, 67, Tables 54, 58. Primary occupation of farming means 50% or more of work time farming. *Id.*, App. B., at 16. Farming was not the primary occupation for 55% of all producers and 54% of male producers. *Id.* at 62, 65, Tables 54 and 56.

10 or fewer years farming experience). Only about 13% of females were the sole producer on their farm; most operated farms with more than one producer. Sales from female-operated farms (\$148 billion) were 38% of total farm sales in 2017, but female producers operated farms with lower sales than farms operated by male producers.¹⁸

3. Programs to Facilitate Access to Agricultural Land

Agricultural land, like other real property in the United States, is freely alienable. Few restrictions impede the transfer of farmland to farmers or other buyers. Moreover, farmers -- men and women -- do not need special qualifications to purchase farmland or to operate farms.

Nonetheless, access to land for purchase or rent is often limited. Little farmland changes ownership each year. US farmers are aging, and one-third of US farmers are older than 65.¹⁹ But most farmland is sold to relatives or transferred to family members through inheritance or gifts. Only a small amount of US farmland is sold to non-relatives.²⁰ Beginning farmers and ranchers, as well as socially disadvantaged operators, often face barriers to obtain farmland. US law facilitates access to agricultural land for beginning farmers,²¹ veterans of military service, socially disadvantaged farmers (African American and other groups), and (in some programs) women farmers. In addition, the US Department of Agriculture (USDA) invests millions of dollars in programs to provide education, training, and technical assistance to beginning, underserved, and veteran farmers and ranchers.²²

For example, the USDA, through the Farm Service Agency (FSA), gives beginning farmers and ranchers priority for some federal loans.²³ FSA makes ownership and operating loans to family-sized farms that cannot obtain credit elsewhere, and the FSA guarantees some loans made by other lenders.²⁴ FSA targets and reserves certain loan funds for beginning²⁵ and socially disadvantaged farmers. Another USDA program guarantees loans made by private sellers who convey farmland to a beginning or socially disadvantaged farmer under a land contract.²⁶ Under the federal Conservation Reserve Program (CRP), land owners whose CRP contract is expiring receive incentives if they sell or lease land to a

¹⁸ NASS, USDA, *Female Producers* (ACH17-11, 2019). Sales and government payments on 62% of female-operated farms were less than \$10,000.

¹⁹ The average age of primary producers in 2022 was 58.1. NASS, *supra* note 7, at 57, Table 52. The average age in 1997 was 54.

²⁰ See generally Scott Callahan & Daniel Hellerstein, *Access to Farmland by Beginning and Socially Disadvantaged Farmers: Issues and Opportunities* (ERS, AP 096, Dec. 2022).

²¹ See NASS, *supra* note 7, at 86, 87, Tables 69, 70 for 2022 Census of Agriculture information on new and beginning producers.

²² USDA, *Underserved and Veteran Farmers, Ranchers, and Foresters (2501 Program)*, <https://www.usda.gov/partnerships/underserved-veteran-farmers-ranchers-foresters>; NIFA, *USDA, Beginning Farmer and Rancher Development Program*, <https://www.nifa.usda.gov/grants/funding-opportunities/beginning-farmer-rancher-development-program>.

²³ See 7 US Code [USC] §§ 1922, 1929, 1935, 1941. A “qualified beginning farmer or rancher,” among other requirements, has not operated a farm or ranch, or has operated for not more than 10 years, and owns no land or a statutorily-limited number of acres. 7 USC § 1991.

²⁴ See Callahan & Hellerstein, *supra* note 20.

²⁵ 7 USC § 1994(b)(2).

²⁶ 7 USC § 1936. A land contract is an installment sale of farmland, under which the buyer goes into possession of the land, but title does not transfer until all contract payments are made.

beginning, veteran, or socially disadvantaged farmer or rancher.²⁷ Some state programs authorize loan guarantees, subsidize interest rates, and encourage leases of farmland to young farmers.²⁸ In most states, business incentives also help to support agriculture and agri-business development for new and existing farmers.²⁹

Qualification for special programs differs among agencies. Definitions of beginning or limited resource farmers and military veterans do not consider gender. The definition of socially disadvantaged groups for FSA loan programs includes persons subject to racial, ethnic, or gender prejudice.³⁰ For some programs under the FSA, women are considered socially disadvantaged farmers. FSA targets its assistance to underserved farmers, specifically including women.³¹

In contrast, the Natural Resources Conservation Service (NRCS), which manages USDA conservation programs,³² does not include women in its definition of historically underserved farmer or rancher -- those who were underserved or subject to discrimination in federal programs. NRCS conservation incentives include operators who are beginning, socially disadvantaged, limited resource, and military veterans.³³ Those who qualify may receive increased compensation for conservation practices and other conservation benefits. Of course, women who fit within NRCS definitions -- for example, as beginning farmers -- would qualify.

A new process offers financial assistance for farm loan borrowers, including women, who faced discrimination in USDA farm loan programs. Authorized by federal law,³⁴ financial assistance is available to farmers who experienced discrimination by USDA personnel prior to 1 January 2021 in FSA ownership, operating, and other loans. Discrimination includes different treatment because of race, color, national origin, gender identity, religion, age, disability, and other factors. Borrowers must submit applications to USDA by 13 January 2024, with payments to be allocated after an independent national administrator reviews all applications.³⁵

²⁷ 16 USC § 3835(f). The program does not include sale or lease specifically to women farmers, but women who are beginning farmers qualify.

²⁸ For detailed information, see National Council of State Agricultural Finance Programs, Types of Programs (2022), <https://stateagfinance.org/types-of-state-ag-loan-programs/>.

²⁹ Emma Kuhns et al., The Use of State Business Incentives to Support Agriculture, *Farmdoc daily* 13:205 (9 Nov. 2023), <https://farmdocdaily.illinois.edu/2023/11/the-use-of-state-business-incentives-to-support-agriculture.html>.

³⁰ 7 USC § 2003(e)(1).

³¹ FSA, USDA, Minority and Women Farmers and Ranchers, <https://www.fsa.usda.gov/programs-and-services/farm-loan-programs/minority-and-women-farmers-and-ranchers/index>.

³² For a brief discussion of conservation programs in the 2018 Farm Bill, along with other land-related issues, see Margaret Rosso Grossman, *Protection of Cultivated Land in the United States: Planning, Conservation, and Agricultural Property Transactions*, 80(1) *Tijdschrift voor Agrarisch Recht* 5-18 (2020).

³³ See 16 USC § 3801(a)(23); 7 USC 2279(a)(5), (6) (defining socially disadvantaged group as those whose members have been subjected to racial or ethnic prejudice). See NRCS, USDA, Historically Underserved Farmers and Ranchers, <https://www.nrcs.usda.gov/getting-assistance/underserved-farmers-ranchers>.

³⁴ Inflation Reduction Act, § 22007, Pub. L. 117-169, 136 Stat. 1818 (16 Aug. 2022). \$2.2 billion is authorized, with a maximum of \$500,000 per recipient, but payments are likely to be less.

³⁵ For more information, see USDA, Inflation Reduction Act Assistance for Producers Who Experienced Discrimination in USDA Farm Loan Programs, <https://www.farmers.gov/loans/inflation-reduction-investments/assistance-experienced-discrimination>.

4. Foreign Ownership of Agricultural Land

A. Federal Law: Disclosure of Foreign Ownership

Federal law does not prohibit foreign ownership of agricultural land,³⁶ but requires detailed reports about foreign ownership. The Agricultural Foreign Investment Disclosure Act of 1978³⁷ (AFIDA) states that any “foreign person who acquires or transfers any interest ... in agricultural land” -- that is, land used for agriculture forestry, or timber -- must report that transaction to the US Secretary of Agriculture within 90 days.³⁸ A “person” is an individual or legal entity. “Foreign person” is defined broadly to include any individual who is not a citizen or permanent resident of the United States, any foreign government, certain entities created under foreign laws or located outside the US, and US entities in which a “significant interest” is held by a foreign person, entity, or government.³⁹

USDA publishes annual reports of foreign holdings, based on data drawn from reports required under AFIDA. The most recent report analyzes foreign ownership through December 2022.⁴⁰ Foreign holdings of all US agricultural land totaled about 43.4 million acres as of 31 December 2022: almost 2% of all US land and 3.4% of privately-owned agricultural land. Between 2021 and 2022, foreign holdings of agricultural land increased by about 3.4 million acres.⁴¹

Foreign holdings exist in all 50 states, with most foreign-owned land in Texas, Maine (mostly forest or timber), and Colorado. The largest increases in foreign-owned agricultural land in 2022 were in Colorado, Alabama, and Michigan. A few states had fewer foreign-owned acres than in 2021. Most foreign holdings are in the South and the West of the United States and occupy only a small percent of each state’s agricultural land. In terms of land use, agricultural land holdings are timber or forest, 48.3%; cropland, 28.3%; pasture and other agricultural land, 21.3%. Only about 2% of foreign holdings are non-agricultural land, such as homesteads and roads.⁴²

Investors from many countries own agricultural land in the United States. Canadians hold 32% of the foreign-held land. Other important investor countries are the Netherlands (12%), Italy and the United Kingdom (6% each), and Germany (5%). Investors from all other countries hold 38% of foreign-held land.⁴³

³⁶ Under the Foreign Risk Review Modernization Act, certain foreign investments in US real estate that might impair national security must be reviewed by the Committee on Foreign Investment in the United States. This includes, e.g., land in “close proximity” to military installations and other government property. 50 USC § 4565; regulations at 31 Code of Federal Regulations [CFR] part 802. For cases involving agriculture, the Secretary of Agriculture shall be included in the Committee. Pub. L. 118-42, § 787 (9 Mar. 2024).

³⁷ 7 USC §§ 3501-3508; regulations at 7 CFR part 781. See also 26 USC § 897 (imposing tax on sales and other transfers of real property held by foreign owners).

³⁸ 7 USC § 3501, supplemented by 7 CFR § 781.3. State Departments of Agriculture receive copies of reports involving land in their states. 7 USC § 3505. “Any interest” includes leaseholds of 10 years or longer.

³⁹ 7 USC § 3508. See 7 CFR § 781.2(k) (defining significant interest).

⁴⁰ Mary Estep et al., *Foreign Holdings of U.S. Agricultural Land Through December 31, 2022* (FSA, USDA, Dec. 2023).

⁴¹ *Id.* at 4. Foreign ownership in 2021 was 40 million acres.

⁴² *Id.* at 4-5. In Maine, foreign owners hold 21.1% of private agricultural land; in Hawaii, 12.8%. *Id.* at 4.

⁴³ *Id.* at 4. Over 11.5 million foreign-held acres are owned by US corporations with foreign shareholders. *Id.* at 231-236.

China, with almost 350,000 acres, was not among the top 10 foreign owners by acreage in 2022, but Chinese holdings were valued at \$1.9 billion. Chinese interests owned less than 1% of foreign-owned agricultural land, with 85% of Chinese ownership in five states.⁴⁴ Nonetheless, some in Congress have expressed concern about Chinese ownership of US agricultural land, and in 2023, bills restricting foreign owners from China and other nations were introduced in the US Congress.⁴⁵

Congress has ordered USDA to “report on foreign investments in agricultural land in the United States, including the impact foreign ownership has on family farms, rural communities, and the domestic food supply” and to develop a system to report and disclose foreign ownership information more efficiently and transparently.⁴⁶ In response, USDA’s Farm Service Agency plans to modernize its process for collecting information, revise its reporting form (FAS-153), and ultimately amend its regulation implementing AFIDA. In December 2023, FSA requested public comment on its proposed FAS-153, its method of collecting information, and its regulatory plans.⁴⁷

Foreign ownership can affect national security, trade, and food security. Disclosure under AIFDA may not reflect the extent of foreign holdings of agricultural land. Improved data collection and stronger enforcement will be needed to avoid inaccuracies, underreporting, errors, omissions, and failure to track foreign-owned farmland over time. More public access to data would enhance transparency.⁴⁸

B. State Restrictions on Foreign Ownership

Although no state prohibits foreign ownership of agricultural land completely, about 24 states have laws that restrict farmland ownership.⁴⁹ Some states expressly permit foreign ownership,⁵⁰ and some have no provisions. Restrictions (and even the definitions of agricultural land and farming) vary among the states. Common state law provisions prohibit ownership by nonresident aliens, impose acreage

⁴⁴ *Id.* at 5, 231. Because some AFIDA reports with owners from multiple countries are recorded as “no predominant country,” Chinese ownership may be under-represented. The 2022 Foreign Holdings document added two reports focused on Chinese landholdings, identifying specific investors and types of land use by state. *Id.* at 254-289. A Chinese firm’s purchase of Smithfield Foods in 2013 increased Chinese ownership, and another increase occurred in 2020-2021. Tori Smith, Foreign Ownership of U.S. Agricultural Land, 16 Mar. 2023, <https://www.americanactionforum.org/research/foreign-ownership-of-u-s-agricultural-land>.

⁴⁵ E.g., the Prohibition of Agricultural Land for the People’s Republic of China Act, H.R. 809 (118th Cong.). More general restrictions have been proposed in the Foreign Adversary Risk Management Act, H.R. 513 (protecting agriculture against harmful foreign influence) and Promoting Agriculture Safeguards and Security Act, S. 168 (restrictions on purchases by 4 countries -- China, Russia, Iran, and North Korea). Another proposal, the Build It in America Act, HR 3938, would impose a 60% excise tax on certain foreign buyers of an interest in agricultural land.

⁴⁶ Pub. L. 117-328, § 773, 136 Stat. 4459 (2022); Pub. L. 117-103, 136 Stat. 49 (2022) (requesting data about ownership by governments of China, Russia, Iran, and North Korea). See Renée Johnson, Foreign Ownership of U.S. Agriculture: Selected Policy Options (CRS, IF12312, 19 Jan. 2023).

⁴⁷ FSA, USDA, Notice, Request for Information on Agricultural Foreign Investment Disclosure Act (AFIDA) FSA-153 Form Modernization and Information Collection Request, 88 Federal Register 87,385-87,393 (18 Dec. 2023).

⁴⁸ Johnson, *supra* note 46. For recent recommendations, see GAO, Foreign Investments in U.S. Agricultural Land (GAO-24-106337, Jan. 2024).

⁴⁹ Laws that prohibit or restrict foreign ownership of private agricultural land: Alabama, Arkansas, Florida, Hawaii, Idaho, Indiana, Iowa, Kansas, Kentucky, Louisiana, Mississippi, Missouri, Montana, Nebraska, North Dakota, Ohio, Oklahoma, Pennsylvania, South Carolina, South Dakota, Tennessee, Utah, Virginia, and Wisconsin. See Micah Brown & Nick Spellman, Statutes Regulating Ownership of Agricultural Land, <https://nationalaglawcenter.org/state-compilations/aglandownership/>. Some of these states also limit or restrict corporate farming.

⁵⁰ An 1887 Illinois statute limited the duration of alien ownership of real property. After repeal of that statute in 1992, aliens may acquire, hold, and dispose of real property without restrictions. 765 ILCS 60/7-8.

limitations, or set time limits on ownership.⁵¹ Reflecting federal concerns, some recent state laws prohibit ownership of farmland and other immovable property by foreign adversaries of the United States.⁵² Moreover, some states require reports of ownership.⁵³

Most Midwest farm states, where agriculture is a critical industry, regulate ownership of agricultural land by nonresident aliens.⁵⁴ In recent years, a majority of states have expressed concern about foreign ownership, and about 36 states have proposed legislation. In 2022, for example Indiana enacted a law that restricts certain agricultural land purchases for crop farming or timber by a foreign business entity and requires reporting of transfers of farmland.⁵⁵ In 2023, 12 states enacted or amended a restrictive law. Other states are considering new restrictions or amendments to strengthen existing laws.⁵⁶

One state recently ordered a Chinese-owned company to divest ownership of farmland and fined the company for failure to disclose its ownership.⁵⁷ In another state, however, plaintiffs have challenged the foreign ownership law on constitutional grounds.⁵⁸

5. Corporate Ownership

Ownership of agricultural land by certain corporations has concerned some important agricultural states. The 2022 Census of Agriculture indicated that 6.7% of US farms were corporations, but only 0.1% of these were not family-owned corporations.⁵⁹ To address the concern of corporate ownership, and perhaps to protect family farms, some states have enacted measures that restrict corporate ownership of agricultural land.

Most states have no restrictions on corporate farmland ownership or corporate farming. In those states corporations are generally free to invest in farmland, carry out agricultural operations, and lease land to producers. Indeed, institutions -- e.g., pension funds, investment banks, and others -- buy agricultural land as profitable investments.

⁵¹ Some laws permit aliens to acquire by devise or descent. Federal reports under AFIDA indicate that every state has foreign investment in farmland, and some acquisitions occurred before states enacted restrictions.

⁵² E.g., Ohio Rev. Stat. § 5301.256 (2023); Louisiana Stat. Ann. § 9:2717.1 (2023). Foreign adversaries are identified by the US Secretary of Commerce and listed in 15 CFR 7.4.

⁵³ E.g., the Illinois Agricultural Foreign Investment Disclosure Act, 765 ILCS 50/1-8. A copy of the federal AFIDA report discussed above complies with the Illinois law.

⁵⁴ See generally National Agricultural Law Center (NALC), Statutes Regulating Ownership of Agricultural Land (last updated 30 Nov. 2023), <https://nationalaglawcenter.org/state-compilations/aglandownership/>.

⁵⁵ Indiana Code Ann. §§ 32-22.3.05 to 3-6.

⁵⁶ NALC, State Proposals on Restricting Foreign Ownership of Farmland, link from <https://nationalaglawcenter.org>.

⁵⁷ Mary Hightower, Arkansas 1st to take enforcement action on foreign-ownership law (17 Oct. 2023), <https://www.uaex.uada.edu/media-resources/news/2023/october/10-17-2023-ark-chinese-farmland.aspx>.

⁵⁸ Shen v. Simpson, No. 4:23-cv-208 (N.D. Fla. 2023) (Chinese plaintiffs challenging Florida's SB 264, effective 1 July 2023).

⁵⁹ NASS, *supra* note 7, at 3, 170-71, Tables 1, 74. Corporations, partnerships, and other legal entities made up 15.3% of farms. Corporate farms averaged 1,182 acres, but many are larger.

Nine states restrict certain corporations from owning farmland or operating farms.⁶⁰ In these states, which represent about one-third of US agricultural land, laws prohibit or limit corporate farming. The laws vary, but some exempt certain family farm corporations. The laws may limit the number of family shareholders, require shareholders to be natural persons, and require a family member to live on the farm or be engaged in farming. Other exemptions may exist (e.g., for some types of livestock production). Corporations that violate the law may be forced to divest their ownership.

Restrictions on corporate ownership are vulnerable to constitutional challenge, often under the Dormant Commerce Clause,⁶¹ and a state law that discriminates against interstate commerce is likely to be invalid. Several federal courts have held that state restrictions on corporate farming violated the Dormant Commerce Clause.⁶² In other states, however, restrictions continue to apply.

6. Conclusion

Agricultural land is critical for production of food and fiber for the United States and for other nations. US farmland is abundant, and that land, especially prime farmland, must be protected from conversion to non-agricultural uses and from degradation. State law governs many aspects of land use, but federal law supports conservation on agricultural land. As the discussion above indicates, both federal and state laws help to ensure that beginning and underserved farmers have access to farmland. Required federal disclosure and state restrictions on foreign ownership play a role in US food security, while state restrictions on corporate ownership may help to protect family farms.

Federal statutes, not discussed in this brief Article, affect agricultural production in the United States and include provisions that support farmers and encourage protection and conservation of vulnerable farmland. For decades, comprehensive federal agricultural statutes (called Farm Bills) have established important agricultural and food policy measures that govern many aspects of rural law in the United States. The Agricultural Improvement Act of 2018, the most recent Farm Bill, established, reauthorized, or amended programs that govern conservation, commodities, crop insurance, credit, nutrition, and many other agricultural activities.⁶³ The US Congress usually enacts a Farm Bill every five years.

Farm Bills are complex laws, and drafts of legislation in the Senate and House are followed by negotiations in Congress. Although Congress was expected to enact a new Farm Bill in 2023, the 2018 Farm

⁶⁰ These include Oklahoma, Nebraska, South Dakota, North Dakota, Wisconsin, Minnesota, Kansas, Missouri, and Iowa. Nebraska and South Dakota have constitutional provisions. See National Agricultural Law Center, Corporate Farming & Land Ownership Laws – An Overview, <https://nationalaglawcenter.org/overview/corporate-farminglaws/>.

⁶¹ The Commerce Clause of the US Constitution authorizes Congress “to regulate commerce ... among the several states.” US Const. art. I, § 8, cl. 3. Even when Congress has not regulated, the so-called Dormant Commerce Clause prohibits states from enacting laws that discriminate against or unreasonably burden interstate commerce.

⁶² E.g., Nebraska Const. art. XII, § 8(1)(A); South Dakota Const., art. XVII, § 21. *Jones v. Gale*, 470 F.3d 1261 (8th Cir. 2006) (discriminatory intent and discrimination on the face of the Nebraska measure); *South Dakota Farm Bureau, Inc. v. Hazeltine*, 340 F.3d 583 (8th Cir. 2003) (discriminatory intent). For cases decided between 1879 and 2023, see National Agricultural Law Center, Case Law Index: Corporate Farming and Land Ownership Laws, <https://nationalaglawcenter.org/aglaw-reporter/case-law-index/corporate-farming-laws/>.

⁶³ Pub. L. 115-334, 132 Stat. 4530 (20 Dec. 2018). The 2018 Farm Bill (529 pages) governs Commodities, Conservation, Trade, Nutrition, Credit, Rural Development, Research and Extension, Forestry, Energy, Horticulture, Crop Insurance, and Miscellaneous programs.

Bill expired 30 September 2023.⁶⁴ Congress made little progress toward new legislation. In a law signed by President Biden in November 2023, Congress extended the 2018 Farm Bill until 30 September 2024.⁶⁵ This extension of the Farm Bill will allow USDA programs to continue until Congress enacts a new law. Provisions of a new Farm Bill, when enacted by Congress and implemented by the US Department of Agriculture and other federal agencies, will affect farming and farmland in the United States for the next five years.

⁶⁴ See Jim Monke et al., *Expiration of the Farm Bill* (CRS R47659, 21 Aug. 2023) (outlining the effect of expiration on Farm Bill programs). After expiration, some programs lacked funding, legal authority to operate, or both. Other programs have permanent authorization and do not expire. The Inflation Reduction Act of 2022, Pub. L. 117-169, 136 Stat. 1818 (16 Aug. 2022), extended some conservation programs through 2031.

⁶⁵ Further Continuing Appropriations and Other Extensions Act, 2024, Pub. L. 118-22, § 102, 137 Stat. 112 (16 Nov. 2023). The Farm Bill extension was part of a stopgap funding bill intended to avoid a government shutdown.